

THE CONTRIBUTION OF PROFESSOR AZIZOVA SAN'AT SABIROVNA TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHARMACOLOGY AND PEDIATRICS SPHERES IN UZBEKISTAN

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San'at Sabirovna Azizova, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Honored Scientist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Academician of the Russian Academy of Medical-Technic Sciences, is a well-known for her scientific, pedagogical and public works and respected scientist not only in Uzbekistan but also in foreign countries.

Azizova San'at Sabirovna was born in Tashkent in 1934 in a intellectuals family. In 1952, she graduated from high school with a gold medal, entered the medical faculty of the Tashkent State Medical Institute, and graduated with honors in 1958. In the same year, she was admitted to postgraduate studies at the pharmacology laboratory of the Institute of Chemistry of Plant Substances of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, and she defended her candidate's thesis in 1963. Her doctoral thesis she defended in 1968.

Professor S.S. Azizova is carrying out scientific investigation

She was first woman in our Republic who the first received the title of candidate of science, doctor of science, and the title of professor in the field of pharmacology

In 1972, she was appointed as the head of the pharmacology department of the newly opened Central Asian Institute of Pediatric Medicine and selflessly worked in the training of national personnel for our Republic. The students were given high-level scientific and ideological lectures, practical training, educational, spiritual and learning activities. Thousands of pediatrician-apprentices trained by the scientist are actively serving in the field of medicine in all cities and districts of our Republic, in Karakalpakstan and neighboring Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan. Active work was also carried out in the TashPMI branch opened in Karakalpakstan. For several years, she went to Nukus, gave lectures and started educational and methodological work. They prepared a candidate of science in the field of pharmacology for the branch.

Signing ceremony of the cooperation agreement with Korea's prestigious university's scholars and the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

S.S.Azizova also contributed to the development of cooperation TashPTI with scientists of the world's leading universities.

S.S.Azizova headed the monothematic commission on the science of pharmacology under the Rectors' Directorate for many years. She carried out great work on the integration of educational and methodological work in medical universities, drawing up model and working plans.

S.S.Azizova devoted her whole life to science and to be a mature scientist was greatly contributed by her parents and her mentor - Professor Isak Kamilovich Kamilov, a doctor who served in Uzbekistan.

S.S. Azizova with the scientific supervisor Professor I.K.Komilov and colleagues Professor N.N. Kompantsev

Professor S.S. Azizova, prof. I.K.Kamilov, prof. N.M. Dmitrieva (Ukraine), and her spouses I.Mukimjonov and others

S.S.Azizova throughout her life studied the effect of various medicinal substances on heart glycosides, cardioprotectors, hepatoprotectors, atherosclerosis and metabolism, and the pediatric features of this field were added in many cases. There is another side to the matter, the scientist was always able to find the most relevant points of theoretical and practical medicine and worked effectively in these directions with his students. As we all know, according to the WHO, cardiovascular diseases are the number one cause of death in many countries. 15 of the 21 candidates of science educated by Azizova are devoted to heart disease. Many drugs have been tried, including saponins, coumarins, flavonoids, cuspidozides, olithoroside, strophantidin. A comparative evaluation of the drugs used in long studies in experimental cardiology was given. In several scientific studies, cobalt ligands were studied and their hepatoprotective properties were determined. In this field, A. Abdusamatov defended his candidacy and doctorate theses, two new drugs were positively recommended by the Pharmacological Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The apprentice of the scientist V.Mazgutov showed a positive effect of the combination of sodium selenite, vitamin E, retabolil drugs in experimental hypotrophy in early ontogeny. S.Azizova made a great contribution to the development of pediatric pharmacology. She performed a lot of practical work in researching the effects of new drugs on the young body, pregnancy in the experimental part, and applying them to medicine. She conducted many experiments and scientific works in the development of pediatric pharmacology.

Along with teaching the science of pharmacology, the scientist gave great importance to the students to be highly spiritual and enlightened, to know the history, values, and traditions of our country and to apply them to life. During lectures, practical sessions and meetings with students, they called future doctors to be devoted to their people, to their country, to be spiritual, to love poetry and art, and they themselves became role models in these fields. San'at Sobirovna was always respected by students and colleagues.

Scientist S.S. Azizova is lecturing students on pharmacology 3rd year students of TashPMI

The scientist who created a scientific school in science trained 7 doctors of science and 22 candidates of science. More than half of our scholar's students are women. Pupils: K.Djuraeva, N.Agzamova, Z.Poluanova, R.Azizova, B.A. Karabekova, Sh.T.Ziyaeva, A.A.Yunusov are associate professors at medical universities, Yu.Mamadov worked as the head of the department of clinical pharmacology of AndMI. A.A.Abdusamatov was a professor and vice-rector for scientific affairs at the department of pharmacology of TashPMI. Currently, S.S.Azizova's students S.D.Aminov-doctor of medical sciences, professor and head the department of pharmacology, N.V.Magzumova-candidate of medical sciences, associate professor and at the department of clinical pharmacology at TashPMI.

Students trained in the scientific schools of Professor S.S.Azizova and staff Pharmacology Department

Professor S.S. Azizova at the department meeting

S.S.Azizova made a great contribution to the development of pediatric pharmacology in our Republic. Scholar is the author of more than 225 scientific works, including 3 textbooks, 3 monographs, 6 author's testimonials, 10 educational and methodological manuals, 3 brochures, articles published in our Republic and in collections and journals of near and far foreign countries. Scientists were able to present and promote the science of Uzbekistan at international congresses and symposia (Prague, Delhi, Tashkent, Sofia, Poznan, Eskisehir-Turkey, Canada).

Delhi 1970. The scientist gives a lecture on the topic "Pharmacology of cardiac glycosides obtained from gyoza growing in Central Asia" at the Indo-Soviet symposium on the chemistry of medicinal substances and their pharmacology

Professor S.S. Azizova is in Austria with the delegation of Uzbekistan

She was awarded the title of Honored Scientist of Uzbekistan in 1992. She participated in the review of the "Ustoz" fund of the Ministry of Higher Education and received the first-class diploma "The best scientific leader of 1998".

Along with scientific-pedagogical works, they also carried out public works at the level of the institute, government, city, district, republic. Deputies elected for 5 convocation sessions of Yunus-abad administration. Worked as the chairman of the Yunus-abad women's committee, the chairman of the Tashkent city women's committee, and the chairman of the regional women's committee. Member of the Plenum, Presidium of the Republican Women's Committee; those awarded with medals, honorary titles. Actively worked in Knowledge and Friendship societies.

The team of the institute has a meeting with the poetess Halima Khudoyberdieva

Professor S.S. Azizova is handing out gifts to women and girls of the institute

Lectures and roundtable discussions were held in cities and districts of our republic. On the referral of the "Science", "Knowledge", "Friendship" societies, She went to many countries in the way of science, knowledge, friendship also participated in international conferences and showed the science and spirituality of Uzbekistan at a high level in countries as the ChSSR, the USA, Canada, Austria, India.

The scientist encouraged his children to selflessly serve science, their people, and their country. Her son Iskandar Ilhamovich Mukimjanov is a candidate of science in cardiology. Daughters Akhmedova Dilorom Ilkhamovna is a well-known scientist in the field of pediatrics, doctor of science, professor, for more than 10 years she was the director of the Republican Center for Scientific and Practical Pediatrics, and now she is the head of the department of pediatrics, folk medicine of the 2nd hospital of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, and Zakirova Nodira Ilkhamovna - candidate of medical sciences, associate professor of the department of neonatology, granddaughter Alieva Nigora Rustamovna - doctor of medical sciences, associate professor, head of the department of pediatrics, folk medicine of the 1st hospital of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute.

Highly appreciated scholar S.S.Azizova's services in training young specialists the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute has established a scholarship named after the scholar for talented students and masters since 2017. To date, 5 students and masters have been awarded the Distinguished Scholar Scholarship named after "PROFESSOR S.S.AZIZOVA".

Professor San'at Sabirovna died in 2013 and would have been 90 years old when she was alive.

A well-known scientist of our republic, a scientist who made a great contribution to the advancement of Uzbekistan's science at the international level, a selfless teacher of our medicine and higher education, a zealous propagator of enlightenment and spirituality, a patriotic scientist - Professor SAN'AT SABIROVNA AZIZOVA will always remain in our hearts and memories.